

High Contrast Imaging

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Example without coronagraphy:

MagAO, various wavelengths
BetaPic b (Morzinski+ 2015)

Example WITH coronagraphy:

SPHERE, NIR, apodized coronagraph

R Aq central part
Faint structures in
VISIBLE

IST-WFP3 (central region)

R Aqr central part
Faint structures in
VISIBLE

Outline

- High contrast imaging : an increasingly active field of research
- Critical needs for high contrast for Calibrations
 - Calibration needed BEFORE operations
 - Specific questions of PSF halo registration
 - Companion information extraction:
 - Astrometry
 - Photometry
 - Polarimetry
- Calibrations within the « ESO approach »
 - From instrument design to operation validation and instrument monitoring
 - Auxiliary data
 - Dealing with various approaches of data reduction: auto-calibration, interest of large data sets ? Generic or specific data reduction ?

High contrast: a rapidly growing field

Brown Dwarf Gliese 229B

Pre-history

Palomar Observatory
Discovery Image
October 27, 1994

Hubble Space Telescope
Wide Field Planetary Camera 2
November 17, 1995

PRC95-48 · ST ScI OPO · November 29, 1995
T. Nakajima and S. Kulkarni (CalTech), S. Durrance and D. Golimowski (JHU), NASA

Bpic: Smith&Terrile 1984

Mouillet+ 1997

Exoplanet and Brown Dwarf imaging: requirements

Pioneering era: everything was already there in early 2000's ?

Projects :

HST (including blocking masks, roll-angle diff imaging)

AO on 8-m telescopes for a wide community: Keck, VLT, Gemini,

Also Palomar, Lyot Project AEOS, Subaru

Uncorrected image
FWHM: 0.50"

Left: uncorrected

Right: corrected

NACO on VLT
Rousset et al 02

AO corrected image
FWHM: 0.07"

1m

From low mass companions to planets ?

Lagrange et al, 2008 (NACO)

Marois et al, 2008 (Gemini, Keck)

- planetary mass companions
- around **A-type dusty** stars or BD
- close to the limit of instrument capabilities

Pioneering era: still missing something ! Differential imaging

Spectral differential imaging (Marois+ 2000, Sparks&Ford 2002, Close&Lenzen 03, ...)
Yes it works ! **But 2nd order effects rapidly damp the performance !**

Pioneering era: still missing something !

Differential imaging

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Yes it works ! **But 2nd order effects rapidly damp the performance !**

Temporal structure: another dangerous killer (even from space !)

Hinkley+ 2007

Barrois+ 2010, Keck.

*Lafrenière+ 2009, HST/
NICMOS*

*Soummer+ 2011, HST/
NICMOS*

Dedicated high contrast imagers For a wide community and large surveys

GPI @ Gemini

@ Cassegrain focus

SPHERE @ VLT

@ Nasmyth focus

High order, high speed « extreme » AO on bright targets
Advanced Coronagraphy (apodized Lyot), under controlled alignment and calibration
Differential techniques: temporal (angular), spectral, and/or polarimetric

Dedicated high contrast imagers For a wide community and large surveys

GPI @ Gemini

SPHERE @ VLT

On-axis central FoV IFU

Spectral dispersion : one band at a time
Or linear polarisation analysis

Y-J range or Y-H (up to 1.65 mic)

Dual band imaging (10'' FoV)

Dual polarization

Long Slit spectro (R~350)

Imaging and diff. Polar. In VISIBLE

Dedicated high contrast imagers

And also :

- Keck, Palomar:
 - new developments, tests, for key concept demonstration including: coronagraphy, speckle calibration and correction, coupling to high resolution spectroscopy
- Subaru/SCEXAO + various NIR and Vis instrument, including the new IFS CHARIS !
- LBT : up to thermal IR
- MagAO : from visible to thermal IR
- ESO/VLT
 - VISIR and high contrast at 10 mic
 - Need to maintain and push performance in L band (ERIS !)
 - Room for even better contrast on SPHERE: faster, closer, deeper.
- ELTs :
 - Closer-in even with the 1st light instruments
 - Towards terrestrial planets characterization for a dedicated design
- And even space, with many common system concepts and calibrations:
 - NASA/WFIRST including a coronagraphic instrument equipped with Deformable mirrors
 - 2 out of 4 concepts for the next major mission (LUVVOIR, HabEx)

High contrast imaging approach and requirements

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- High contrast imaging : an increasingly active field of research
- **Critical needs for high contrast for Calibrations**
 - **Calibration needed BEFORE operations**
 - **Specific questions of PSF halo registration**
 - **Companion information extraction:**
 - **Astrometry**
 - **Photometry**
 - **Polarimetry**
- Calibrations within the « ESO approach »
 - From instrument design to operation validation and instrument monitoring
 - Auxiliary data
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Calibrations / checks BEFORE operations

- Adaptive Optics servo loop-related calibrations
 - Active mirror – sensor registration (« interaction matrices »)
 - Deformable Mirror shape at rest (« offset voltages » + handling DM thermal dependency)
 - Sensors references
 - Internal alignment check (in particular pupil)
- On-coronagraph centering registration
- Post-AO Optical aberrations (« Non Common-Path Aberrations » = NCPA) : see next part
- Any blind (open-loop) settings:
 - All tracking devices (up to 5 in SPHERE): reference points and control laws
 - Tabulated pre-compensations (eg chromatism)

PSF halo registration/subtraction

- Causes for post-coronagraph halo = **aberrations** (+ coronagraph non-ideal limitations):
 - Turbulence residuals: non-corrected atmosphere, internal turbulence
 - Quasi-static optical defects

The diagram illustrates the decomposition of a coronagraphic PSF. On the left is the total PSF, which is a bright central spot surrounded by a diffuse, noisy halo. This is shown to be approximately equal to the sum of two components. The first component is a noisy, speckle-like pattern representing turbulence residuals. The second component is a clean, smooth PSF with a bright central spot and a dark, well-defined halo, representing the PSF after subtraction of the turbulence residuals.

$$h_{\lambda}^c(\delta_u, S_{\delta_r}) \approx \left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\right)^2 \left[|\tilde{p}_d * \tilde{\delta}_u|^2 \right] + \left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\right)^2 \left[\tilde{p}_d^2 * S_{\delta_r} - \left\langle |\tilde{p}_d * \tilde{P}(\delta_r)|^2 \right\rangle \right]$$

From Ygouf et al 2012

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A posteriori handling: differential imaging of different flavours:

- Angular differential imaging: speckle lifetime analysis ?

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A posteriori handling: differential imaging of different flavours:

- Angular differential imaging
- Spectral differential imaging

: IFS Y-H

At 1st order: speckles spread linearly with λ . Requires low aberration regime, no system chromaticity.

Auto-calibration (eg MEDUSAE algorithm: Ygouf et al 2012): under study

PSF halo registration/subtraction

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A posteriori handling: differential imaging of different flavours:

- Angular differential imaging
 - Spectral differential imaging
 - Polarimetric differential imaging
 - Reference/Binary differential imaging
-
- But all limited by remaining part of uncontrolled/uncommon aberrations, typically at the level of handful of nm rms

PSF halo registration/subtraction

- Causes for post-coronagraph halo limitations):
 - Turbulence residuals: non-correlated
 - Quasi-static optical defects

A posteriori handling: differential imaging
quality to start with, and then, best known
(on-going research)

See Poster Schmid+

Turbulent part:

- Directly related to AO performance: motivating and AO upgrade ???
Technology maturity allows significant improvement
- Impact of variable correction is most sensitive at short wavelength !
- Dependent on conditions (especially along wind direction, and for anti aliasing)

PSF halo registration/subtraction

- Causes for post-coronagraph halo = **aberrations** (+ coronagraph non-ideal limitations):
 - Turbulence residuals: non-corrected atmosphere, internal turbulence
 - Quasi-static optical defects

A posteriori handling: differential imaging of different flavours: still requires best quality to start with, and then, best knowledge to guide PSF subtraction algos (on-going research)

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- Making use of AO real-time data ?

SPHERE AO data from main wavefront sensor and IR tilt sensor

2014-12-17

PSF halo registration/subtraction

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Turbulent part:

- Directly related to AO performance: motivating and AO upgrade ??
Technology maturity allows significant improvement
- Impact of variable correction is most sensitive at short wavelength !
- Dependent on conditions (especially along wind direction, and for anti aliasing)
- Making use of AO real-time data ? Different uses on different timescales
 - Minutes: overall monitoring, data quality control, non-coronagraph PSF check
 - Seconds: possible direct support to frame selection, data reduction, SR monitoring and support to photometry
 - Milli-seconds: combined use together with high speed science data ??

PSF halo registration/subtraction

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Turbulent part

Quasi-static optical defects:

- Worth to correct wrt turbulent defects ? Different amplitude, timescales, impacts
- How to measure ? Concept ? During or before observations ?
- How to use the information a posteriori ?

Low aberration measurements ?

- Different ideas:
 - SPHERE initial idea: phase diversity on internal source before night
 - GPI / Palomar approach : « CAL » system = interferometric monitoring of low level and slow aberrations
 - On-science detector measurement (« focal-plane sensors »):
 - eg coherence probe of the speckles (unlike companion incoherent light) through temporal (Guyon+, Give'lon+) or spatial (Baudoz +)
 - Spectral diversity and instrument model : COFFEE approach (Paul+)
 - ZELDA: imaging pupil phase defects from a focal phase mask (N'Diaye+)
- Key choices:
 - during observation (through turbulence residuals !) → Servo-loop compensation
 - Before obs on internal source → static compensation
 - Information for a posteriori data reduction → no compensation
 - Or a combination, depending on defect timescales

Low aberration measurements ? Illustration in case of ZELDA

- Initially used in SPHERE for instrument qualification purposes
- Also the « discoverer » of the « low-wind effect » associated to air-spider thermal exchange and strong PSF degradation in many telescopes

Sauvage et al. AO4ELT

Low aberration measurements ? Illustration in case of ZELDA

ZELDA on internal source

Before correction

After correction

Before correction
[filtered]

After correction
[filtered]

30 nm rms within « corrected region »

16 nm rms after correction, inc. remaining tilt

PSF halo registration/subtraction

- Causes for post-coronagraph halo = **aberrations** (+ coronagraph non-ideal limitations):
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Open research : in the middle of servo-loop operation, calibration and data reduction

Companion information extraction

- From raw data to reduced data images in each spectral channel

Companion information extraction

- From raw data to reduced data images in each spectral channel

- Generic data extraction from 2D raw data to x, y, λ cubes
- Flat field requirements: dependencies over-estimated
- Critical items (combined):
 - Spaxel footprint registration
 - Signal vs background extraction:
 - Large scale thermal background (T dependent)
 - Spaxel to spaxel cross-talk (local)

Note on wavelength calibration: internal calibration or auto-calibration ?

Companion information extraction

- From raw data to reduced data images in each spectral channel
- PSF subtraction : see previous part

Companion information extraction

- From raw data to reduced data images in each spectral channel
- PSF subtraction : see previous part
- **Astrometry:** ~mas accuracy needed wrt host star for
 - Companion vs background star distinction (proper motion analysis)

Eg for 51 Eri b discovery paper, Macintosh+ 2015

Companion information extraction

- From raw data to reduced data images in each spectral channel
- PSF subtraction : see previous part
- **Astrometry** : ~mas accur
 - Companion vs back
 - Orbit analysis

Eg for HR8799 system, Maire+ 2015
See also Zurlo+ 2016, ...

Fig. 1. LMIRCam image in L' band of the HR 8799 multiple-planet

- From rav
- PSF subtr
- Astrome
 - Con
 - Orbi

Eg for HR8799
Wertz+ 2016

- From rav
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Eg for HR8799
Wertz+ 2016

Companion information extraction

- From raw data to reduced data images in each spectral channel
- PSF subtraction : see previous part
- Astrometry: difficulties and calibration/extraction approaches
 - platescale, **orientation**, distortion calibration, (see Maire+ 2016) with special care to:
 - Small Field of View (combination of internal calibration)

Companion information extraction

- From raw data to reduced data images in each spectral channel
- PSF subtraction : see previous part
- **Astrometry**: difficulties and calibration/extraction approaches
 - platescale, **orientation**, distortion calibration, (see Maire+ 2016) with special care to:
 - Small Field of View (combination of external primary calibrators and internal calibration)
 - Apparent orientation in pupil-stabilized mode = de-rotator control:
 - Hardware fine control
 - Software control (INS control in relation to VLT SW, data reduction analysis, frame timing...)

Companion information extraction

- From raw data to reduced data images in each spectral channel
- PSF subtraction : see previous part
- **Astrometry**: difficulties and calibration/extraction approaches
 - platescale, **orientation**, distortion calibration, (see Maire+ SPIE 2016)
 - Star position (under coronagraph !) registration:
 - Overall halo global analysis, frame-to-frame analysis
 - Specific stellar replica produced by pupil (phase or amplitude) symmetric pattern

Fig. 1. Histogram of the horizontal and vertical offsets of the star with respect to the center of the frame in the 5 December (right) data cube.

Eg for HR8799 Wertz+ 2016

Companion information extraction

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 - Specific stellar replica produced by pupil (phase or amplitude) symmetric pattern
 - Companion faint signal extraction over (correlated) speckle noise

Eg for HR8799 Wertz+ 2016

Fig. 6. Speckle noise estimation for HR8799b observed on 6 December 2014. The histograms illustrate the offsets between the true position/flux

Companion information extraction

- From raw data to reduced data images in each spectral channel
- PSF subtraction : ADI, SDI, RDI , PDI, BDI
- Astrometry
- **Photometry:** relative to the central star
 - As for astrometry: the star is hidden behind coronagraph !
 - Off-mask PSF core observation (with – calibrated !– neutral densities) before and after
 - Handling SR variation during the deep exposure ?
 - « waffle replica » ? , AO-supported information ? To be consolidated
 - Faint companion signal over speckle noise, and impact of PSF halo subtraction !

- From
- PSF su
- Astror
- Photc
 - A

- F_λ
- St

Eg for 51Eri b, Macintosh+ 2015

Figure S2: 51 Eri b spectra from the three different pipelines. The *H*-band spectra agree well while at *J*-band, the discrepancies are explained by the combination of the low S/N and the presence of a close by negative speckle of similar intensity that the pipelines treat differently.

Companion information extraction

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 - Off-mask PSF core observation (with – calibrated !– neutral densities) before and after
 - Handling SR variation during the deep exposure ?
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 - Faint companion signal over speckle noise, and impact of PSF halo subtraction !
 - Speckle noise to be included into uncertainty estimations, including discussion on temporal/spectral correlations !
 - Include in a consistent manner PSF subtraction operation for companion flux estimates
 - Correction estimates with test « fake companions »
 - Analytical/numerical estimate of flux loss (« forward modeling », Pueyo+ 2015, ...)
 - Built-in search for corrected companion pattern, separate detection approach from photometry (ANDROMEDA algorithm approach)

SNR map

One channel detection map

Multi-channel detection map

ANDROMEDA approach:

- Search for the known companion pattern (if present) within speckle residuals: multi-channel approach
- Estimate the most-probable flux, at pre-defined position

(from F. Cantalloube PhD. Samland+ 2017 in revision)

Polarimetry

- Another differential technique very efficient for reflected/scattered light, down to very short separations

HR4796A: Perrin+2015 (GPI)

See also Milli+ 2017 (SPHERE)

Polarimetry

- Another differential technique very efficient for reflected/scattered light, down to very short separations
- Keeping instrumental polarization under control requires strong design caution: few and low inclination reflexions, and/or compensate for induced polarisation
- Status on SPHERE in NIR: high efficiency in J, strong function of de-rotator orientation in other bands (induces restrictions on user-defined field orientations)
- Status on SPHERE in VISIBLE :
 - higher instrumental polar is compensated for automatically down to $< \sim 0.5\%$ (for all pointing directions and filters)
 - Very high differential imaging capability
 - Limitation associated to sub-mas birefringent tilt !
- In Future: higher contrast performance should include more and more caution on polar-dependent aberrations (eg : future space-based coronagraphs)

Building-up, scientific, technology, instrument expertise On ground-based 8-m telescopes

How deep can we probe visible reflected light ?

- Ferro-electric polarization modulator (1 kHz)
- Synchronous demodulating CCD (in visible)
- → images of 2 polarizations measured quasi-simultaneously, through same optics, on same pixels !

Coronagraphic medium R band, no density !

(Unauthorized) spying image in NIR (NBF, full density...)

Coronagraphic medium R band, no density,

(authorized) spying image in NIR
(full density...)

Polar signal residuals with / without beamshift correction
Better than 10^{-6} at 200 mas ! (Schmid et al, in progress)

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- **Calibrations within the « ESO approach »**
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« Calibrations » within operational context and instrument development

- Calibration plan and instrument design:
 - PDR and FDR extensive work proved to be essential:
 - Hardware part for calibration is significant !
 - Software design heavily impacted (strong interface between in-operation compensation and calibration)
 - Strong impact on performance budget analysis
 - A significant work needed post commissioning !!
 - Sure we want the full quality of procedures before tests on sky ?
 - Provision (more) resource for that period
 - Involvement of ESO staff and operation expertise is essential in this phase
 - Converging to a final calibration plan in operation context:
 - ESO calibration supporting tools (regular, observation-dependent calibration needs, missing calibration detection, calibration QC monitoring...) = extremely valuable
 - In a preliminary phase: a set of pre-defined system cal blocks could also probably cover most of the needs...

« Calibrations » within operational context and instrument development

- Calibration plan and instrument design
- On-sky calibrations:
 - Astrometry: in particular orientation (« true North »)
 - Absolute photometry is not critical
- Science data, program optimization and AO :
 - Any prevision of turbulence → could be essential in for optimal program scheduling !
 - A posteriori : AO provides important diagnosis of turbulence:
 - Could be useful at observatory level ?
 - Use of these data in support to data reduction can become increasingly important !

« Calibrations » within operational context and instrument development

- Calibration plan and instrument design
- On-sky calibrations:
- Science data, program optimization and AO :
- Large data sets, calibration, and data reduction:
 - **This is on-going research !**
 - We should expect evolution of data reduction procedures → re-processing of very large data sets
 - Synergy with signal processing research is increasingly important: interest of auto-calibration (even better use of a priori knowledge of the instrument) ? Impact of « co-conception » ?
 - **Large data sets** allow PSF characterization and subtraction approaches that are becoming more and more important in advanced papers: better subtraction (eg « ALICE » program on HST/NICMOS !) , qualification of uncertainties, correlation analysis...

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 - **Large data sets** allow PSF characterization and subtraction approaches that are becoming more and more important. Interest expertise gathering, procedure comparison (eg Vortex Team), large scale data crunching capability, handling large data sets... (SPHERE Data Center, ...)